

COMPOUNDS OF NICKEL IODIDE WITH AMINES AND HETEROCYCLIC BASES

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Several compounds of nickel iodide with amines have been prepared by the action of primary (mono and di), secondary and tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases on nickel iodide in ether, their properties studied and their structures discussed.

Nickel usually exhibits a co-ordination number of six, but compounds in which it is four are also reported in literature. Erdmann (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1866, 97, 395) and Laurent (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1852, 36, 353) obtained $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_4](\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by the action of ammonia on $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. Ephraim and Moser (*Ber.*, 1920, 53, 548) prepared $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{A}_2$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{B}_2$ and showed that the formation of ammines with more than six ammonia groups in salts of small cation and large organic anion was independent of the presence of organic residues. Spacu (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1924, II, 2650) obtained $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2)_2] \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \cdot (\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2)_2] \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ by mixing an alcoholic solution of nickel nitrate with benzidine in alcohol. Rammelsberg (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1839, 46, 119) claimed to have prepared tetrammino-nickel iodide by the action of ammonia on nickel iodide. Blitz and Fetkenheuer (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1913, 83, 163) obtained $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_2]\text{I}_2$ by thermal decomposition of hexammino derivative. Ephraim (*Ber.*, 1921, 54B, 379) prepared $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{I}_2$ to 6I_2 , $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{I}_2 \cdot \text{HgI}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{I}_2 \cdot \text{HgI}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the formation of the compounds of nickel iodide with amines and heterocyclic bases.

EXPERIMENTAL

The amines and nickel iodide used were of B.D.H. pure quality, and ether was distilled over sodium.

General Method of Preparation.—A dilute ethereal solution of amine was added to nickel iodide solution in ether with constant shaking till the precipitation was complete and the amine was in slight excess. In some cases, the precipitate was obtained only at a low temperature and, hence, the mixture was kept in a refrigerator. It was filtered, washed with anhydrous ether till the washings did not give any precipitate with nickel iodide. It was dried at the room temperature, analysed and its properties studied.

Iodine was estimated as silver iodide and nickel as dimethylglyoxime complex. The organic matter was found by difference.

TABLE I

Amine	Compounds formed.	Colour.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.		% Iodine.		% Organic substances.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
<i>α</i> -Naphthylamine	4- <i>α</i> -A. NiI ₂ [Ni(C ₁₀ H ₇ NH ₂) ₄]I ₂	Dark green	101°	5.20	5.27	28.60	28.69	66.20	66.04
<i>β</i> -Naphthylamine	4- <i>β</i> -A. NiI ₂ [Ni(C ₁₀ H ₇ NH ₂) ₄]I ₂	Do	20°	5.16	5.27	28.52	28.69	66.32	66.04
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	4-A. NiI ₂ [Ni(C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ NH ₂) ₄]I ₂	Bluish grey	22°	7.80	7.93	33.98	34.28	58.22	57.709
Benzylamine	4-A. NiI ₂ * [Ni(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ NH ₂) ₄]I ₂	Bluish pink		7.86	7.93	33.82	34.28	58.32	57.79
Benzidine	2-A. NiI ₂ [NiC ₁₂ H ₈ (NH ₂) ₂]I ₂	Dark blue	102°	11.71	11.82	50.89	51.12	38.40	37.06
<i>o</i> -Dianisidine	2-A. NiI ₂ [Ni {CH ₃ O(NH ₂)C ₆ H ₃ C ₆ H ₃ NH ₂ OCH ₃ } ₂]I ₂	Bluish green	164°	10.40	10.51	44.86	45.44	44.74	44.05
<i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine	2-A. NiI ₂ [Ni {C ₆ H ₄ (NH ₂) ₂ } ₂]I ₂	Dark blue	168**	10.89	11.11	47.96	48.03	41.15	40.86
<i>p</i> - "	2-A. NiI ₂ [Ni {C ₆ H ₄ (NH ₂) ₂ } ₂]I ₂	Do	260°	10.96	11.11	47.94	48.03	41.20	40.86
<i>o</i> -Tolidine	2-A. NiI ₂ [Ni(CH ₂ NH ₂ C ₆ H ₃ C ₆ H ₃ NH ₂ CH ₂) ₂]I ₂	Bluish grey	240°	7.86	7.97	33.52	34.45	58.22	57.582
Phenylhydrazine	2-A. NiI ₂ [Ni(C ₆ H ₅ NH NH ₂) ₂]I ₂	Yellow	18°	10.80	11.11	47.89	48.03	41.31	40.86
Diphenylamine	4-A. NiI ₂ [Ni {C ₆ H ₅ NH } ₂]I ₂	Light green	158°	5.87	5.94	24.98	25.61	69.15	68.46
Dibenzylamine	4-A. NiI ₂ * [Ni {C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ NH } ₂]I ₂	Bluish green		5.02	5.33	22.89	23.07	72.09	71.59
Triethylamine	1-A. NiI ₂ [Ni(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ N]I ₂	Yellow	174°	14.06	13.82	62.08	61.76	23.86	44.42
Triethylamine	4-A. NiI ₂ [Ni {C ₂ H ₅ N } ₄]I ₂	Do	179°	7.85	8.00	35.92	35.50	56.23	56.44
Diethylaniline	4-A. NiI ₂ * [Ni {C ₆ H ₅ N } ₄]I ₂	Dark blue		6.29	6.32	26.20	28.26	65.51	65.42
Piperazine	4-A. NiI ₂ [Ni(C ₄ H ₈ N ₂) ₄]I ₂	Bluish green	210**	8.94	8.94	38.69	38.67	52.57	52.39
Piperidine	4-A. NiI ₂ [Ni(C ₅ H ₁₀ NH) ₄]I ₂	Greenish yellow	139°	8.90	9.00	19.42	19.44	71.68	71.55

** Decomposed at its melting point.

† A stands for corresp. amine.

* Liquid compounds.

Heterocyclic bases.

Properties.—The co-ordination number of nickel in all the cases studied is four. In the case of triethylamine, however, a precipitate is formed with one molecule of the amine which dissolves on further addition of the amine solution and is reprecipitated. The compounds are stable in dry atmosphere but decompose when treated with strong acids. They are sparingly soluble or insoluble and fairly stable in cold water but decompose slowly on boiling. On heating alone, they decompose and iodine is liberated.

It appears that the amines and heterocyclic bases attach themselves to the central atom, chelate compounds being formed in the case of diamines and can be represented as $[\text{Ni}(4\text{A})]\text{I}_2$ where A is a primary, secondary or tertiary amine or a heterocyclic base and $[\text{Ni}(2\text{D})]\text{I}_2$ where D is a diamine. In the case of secondary and tertiary amines, the reaction is similar to that with the primary amines with the difference that the precipitate appears only on shaking the mixture for a long time at the room temperature, showing thereby the weak co-ordination power of :NH and :N groups.

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